

A STUDY ON STUDENT CENTRIC MODEL FOLLOWED BY UNIVERSITIES WITH REFERENCE TO STUDENTS OF MANGALORE

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ABSTRACT

The term student-centered learning describes the shift in power from the expert teacher to the student learner, driven by a need for a change in the traditional environment where in this ‘so-called educational atmosphere, students become passive, apathetic and bored’. In the College system, the concept of Student-centered education has been derived, in particular, from the idea that the teacher should not ‘interfere with this process of maturation, but act as a guide’. It was highlighted that this was linked with the process of development or ‘readiness’, i.e., the student will learn when he/she is ready.

Through this paper made an attempt to study how student centric model affected learning style of students in Mangalore. In this study both direct interview and secondary data has been taken into consideration.

Keywords: student centric, universities, learning style, teacher

INTRODUCTION

Since the last 50 years or more, there have been significant changes made to the educational system as a whole. With teachers providing direct instruction and few to no possibilities for student interaction or empowerment during learning, the traditional educational system has been heavily teacher-centered[1]. The traditional classroom model has seen significant change over the past ten years due to a shift in the way that content is delivered. Teachers now employ a variety of student-centered learning methodologies to equip, prepare, and develop students who are ready to flourish beyond graduation (McMillan, 2020). The term "student-centered learning," sometimes known as "learner-centered education," refers to teaching strategies that shift the emphasis of instruction away from the teacher and onto the pupil[2]. The development of learner independence and autonomy was initially highlighted by student-centered learning. Change starts with the teacher in classrooms that are student-centered. Student participation in the overall planning, implementation, and evaluation processes is necessary for student-centered learning strategies (McMillan, 2020). The first focus of student-centered learning is on their interests, acknowledging the importance of their voice in the learning process. In a classroom where learning is student-centered, students take on the role of the facilitator and decide what they will study, how they will pace their learning, and how they will evaluate their own learning. This is in contrast to traditional education, sometimes known as "teacher-centered learning," which places the teacher in a predominantly "active" role while students adopt a more "passive"[3], receptive role. This pedagogy recognises the importance of student voice in the learning process for each and every learner and calls for pupils to take an active role in their own education. Teaching and learning should be adapted to the broadest possible scope in order to take advantage of this. The staff and students must have complete discretion over the course of study's content, how teachers and students use their time, and the choice of instructional pedagogies and materials. Like many

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developing nations, India has been working for years to implement reforms like the SarvaShiksha Abhiyan (SSA) programme, the National Curriculum Framework (NCF), and the Right to Education Act (RTE) 2009 to move away from "teacher centered" to "learner-centered" classrooms [1].

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

This study sought to understand:

- How a student-centered model (SCM), also known as the Lerner model, encourages active participation in learning.
- To understand student-centered **learning strategies** and the **advantages** and **issues** related to SCM.
- To understand the essential **Methods** of effective student-centered learning.
- To suggest some changes on idea SCL based on study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

In this study direct interview method and secondary data through some Published papers and articles are used.

LEARNING STRATEGIES OF SUCCESSFUL STUDENT-CENTRED LEARNING:

Learning Strategies of Student-centered Learning for academic achievement and building skills like resilience, independence, creativity, and collaboration are:

- **Productive interconnectedness:** A teacher who models positive interconnectedness in a group is conscious of how each individual's responsibilities affect the group as a whole. The student's fight for success is aided by this more definite accountability (Johnson & Johnson, 2005)[5]. Similarly, after forming constructive dependencies, kids understand that each member's contribution is crucial to the success of the entire group.
- **Personal accountability** is necessary for effective student-centered learning. Each participant in this type of work is assessed against a reliable parameter before reporting their findings to the group and the individual (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). Student-centered learning has a greater rate of performance when planned individual accountability is in place; claim Hooper, Ward, Hannifin, and Clark (1989). Students also need to comprehend that they are in charge of So order to finish a personal project, pupils must also comprehend that they are in charge of their tasks for the faction. Scrounging is not allowed because everyone should have a say in attaining the group's objectives (Gillies, 2007)[6]. When students acquire new skills and teach them to their group members, their sense of self-efficacy increases. As a result, students are compelled to put in more effort to guarantee the success of the team.
- **Cheerful interaction:** This is yet another crucial element of student-centered learning (Gillies, 2007). When students interact physically and witness face-to-face dialogical talks to assess the group's work, they are engaging in constructive communication (Gillies, 2007). Another instance of constructive communication is when students encourage other team members to reach the group's objectives (Johnson & Johnson, 2008). Promotive interaction, according to Johnson and Johnson (2009), requires students to share resources, have faith in one another, assist classmates successfully, maintain concentration for the benefit of the group, and make sure that classmates' problems are helpful in achieving the group's objectives. Learners who connect closely with others and are skilled at deciphering

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body language, vocal cues, and nonverbal signals are better equipped to collaborate and cope with others in interpersonal situations.

- **Appropriate use of social skills:** Social skills, tasks, and good group work are required for student-centered learning to occur (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). The use of communal and group intelligence must be taught to and supported in students if the goal is to reach brilliance through student-centered learning (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). The group's members must care about newcomers and make them feel welcome if it is to achieve its universal goals. They must also effectively network, become familiar with and trust other group members, and find obvious solutions to common conflicts. To effectively work together and handle pressure levels, members must possess some of the aforementioned social and group skills, which eventually consist of the basic links between them.
- **Cluster processing:** In the end, student-centered learning requires the use of cluster processing. Students must come to an agreement on which activities should be changed or kept the same, and they must also reflect on any actions that were either fruitless or useful. Cluster processing is used to examine and broaden the actions that members took, assisting the entire group in achieving their goals (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). Furthermore, because students want to increase the range of possibilities at their disposal in order to accomplish their objectives, cluster processing incorporates a determining evaluative component (Gillies, 2007). It is anticipated that elements will work harder to improve real or imagined group insufficiencies as a result of reflecting on the diligent work of other group members.

METHODS OF STUDENTS' CENTRED LEARNING:

1. **Personalized learning** is a student-centered method in which the student's interests and culture are taken into account and integrated into their education. While this may undoubtedly involve the student in the learning process, it only makes up a small part of an overall student-centered strategy (Jay, 2016)[7].

2. **Choice Boards:** Students can select the tasks they will perform to hone a skill or demonstrate understanding using choice boards. With this method of teaching, teachers differentiate their lessons while giving students opportunities for ownership and empowerment. Choice boards can be used for more than just assessment; they can also be used to familiarise students with new content, provide additional practise, or combine different elements of a lesson or unit.

3. **Puzzle:** By integrating the Puzzle approach with previous concepts, a center/station strategy was developed. In the most basic form of this approach, students work together to try to put the "puzzle" together. Each student is in charge of a certain knowledge component, after which they each apply their knowledge to a larger body of work (puzzle). In order to support the Jigsaw strategy's individual or small-group knowledge piece and facilitate activities like presentations, discussions, competitions, and other methods of learning demonstration, teachers set up stations and centres in their classrooms at the elementary, middle, and high school levels.

4. **Inquiry-Based Learning:** This approach to learning emphasises and fosters students' questions, concepts, and analyses while focusing on their point of view in relation to a specific open question. Within inquiry-based learning, various contents of a lesson can be case studies, group projects, and research projects, among others. More in-depth links to the material provide occasions for students to hone skills that are treasurable in the world in which we dwell.

5. **Project-Based Learning (PBL) and Problem-Based Learning (PBL):** Teachers have their own educational lingo, and "PBL" is frequently used in teacher conversations. The use of project-based learning and problem-based learning as instructional techniques is increasing. In project-based

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learning, students engage on more involved assignments that lead to the production of a unique presentation or final product. With the instructor acting as a facilitator of the students' work and progress, this learning technique strongly relies on the collaboration, communication, and creativity of the students. Through definition, research, and analysis of the problem's causes, students work cooperatively to evaluate potential solutions to the chosen problem, solve it, or present their results. Problem-based learning also includes shorter projects that look at contemporary issues. These two methods of learning make use of comparable, practical connections to the outer world, providing students valuable experience with problem solving and critical thinking opportunities that will behave them after graduation.

6. Flipped classrooms: Teachers constantly explore for methods to utilise class time most effectively. The utilisation of a flipped classroom is a learning technique that takes this into account. In this teaching method, teachers combine many of the previously discussed tactics, such as choice boards or jig sawing, to give students a choice in their learning. Novel or introductory content is presented to students outside of the classroom. Readings, films, pre-recorded presentations, direct instruction, and research assignments can all be used as learning resources (McMillan, 2020).

STUDENT-CENTRED LEARNING CURRICULUM:

The course material is really helpful to students. The curriculum provides students with written information on the kinds of learning experiences they must have in order to meet the intended learning objectives. The learning objectives are made familiar to them through the curriculum. In this approach, learning tasks become more goal-oriented. Because they are aware of the kinds of behavioural modifications anticipated as learning outcomes from studying a certain subject or engaging in a particular activity to supplement learning, this determination drives them to learn.

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF STUDENT-CENTRED LEARNING:

1. Students acquire knowledge that will benefit them throughout their lives as well as other abilities, like learning.
2. It may promote self-esteem and the development of social skills.
3. Additionally, pupils benefit more from their classmates' emotional and intellectual support.
4. Learning about the interplay of rights and obligations.
5. Learners come to realise that education is fascinating and enjoyable.
6. Work assigned to teachers is less routine.
7. The class is being attended to and the students are more willing to participate.
8. A reduction in complaints regarding unfairness and irrelevance
9. Student papers and reports help teachers build their knowledge base of pertinent data.
10. The student is more involved in their own education.
11. Students might modify their learning styles to increase the efficacy of their education.
12. Weak pupils should be paired with more capable students to serve as scaffolding in this type of group activity.
13. Students engage in groups to complete tasks or solve problems, with both individual and group responsibility for conceptual knowledge.
14. Students cooperate to accomplish tasks by preserving group rules.
15. Students are actively encouraging one another and working together to succeed.
16. Active participation as peer tutors to increase the achievement of the group

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17. Student interaction that helps them become more argumentative. In addition to these advantages of cooperative learning also has shortcomings, according to Dees including the following:

Disadvantage

1. Since pupils need more time, it is challenging to meet curriculum goals.
2. Give teachers enough of time so that they will not want to employ cooperative learning in general.
3. Because it takes specialised knowledge from teachers, not all teachers can implement cooperative learning.
4. Particular demands made by a student's personality, such as the need for collaboration.

FINDINGS:

Student-centered learning is now clearly visible at the school level, but it is still underdeveloped, misunderstood, and usually applied in college settings utilising the traditional teacher-centered paradigm. To guarantee the effectiveness of student-centered learning, nothing is being done. SCL has only been adopted by a small number of institutions that offer professional-oriented courses, which frequently gives students the impression that they must take it in order to prepare for future challenges rather than that they want to. Prioritization must be given to the need to improve SCL. Instead of a more straightforward educational system and learning, SCL should help students develop higher concepts and useful knowledge. Among the issues that require focus are:

1. It is essential to stress the importance of student participation in student-centered learning.
2. By collaborating in teams, students will learn material and get ready for future challenges.
3. In a change from the typical teaching style, students will actively participate in class.
4. When students actively seek out knowledge, unfairness and relevance are less likely.
5. More tasks or problems are undertaken, assisting pupils in developing their practical skills.
6. Longer curriculum completion periods might cause problems for teachers.
7. Teacher qualifications are also in doubt for the effectiveness of SCL.

SUGGESTIONS:

According to this research, we may need to reinvent SCL for each new environment rather than enforcing a rigid predetermined model of SCL practises on Indian instructors. It is more important for teachers or college to develop a commitment to a core set of learner-centered beliefs, on the basis of which they can then bring changes in their own practise in alignment with these beliefs, rather than training them to mindlessly comply with a set of external "learner-centered" practises. Teachers cannot be forced into holding specific views, but through teacher education, one can foster an environment in which they can become aware of their current beliefs (which may be oppressive), start to question them, and then decide what kind of values they want to support. Teachers should be provided with enough training and should set a proper plan to complete curriculum on time with SCL.

CONCLUSION:

This study concentrated on the advantages of student-centered learning and how a student can attain it. In a nation like India, where change is slow to take hold and where teacher-centered learning is still the norm, knowing the benefits of student-centered learning makes it simple to advocate for it because it is students, not teachers, who will interact with the outside world.

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Students will gain greater benefits from student-centered learning if they accept it. However, greater teacher cooperation was needed for SCL to succeed.

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